

For each dataset/datatype listed in Column A, a short description is provided (column B). The workflow step of the eDNAAqua-Plan digital landscape (<https://zenodo.org/records/16090825>) (Column C), the methodology to which the dataset applies (metabarcoding, metagenomics, targeted assays) (Column D), the recommended metadata standard vocabulary (Column E) and the recommended public repositories/in-house datamanagement systems (Column F) are listed. Standardised file names for certain datasets are also included and follow the FAIR guidelines (Column G; Project_id, assay_name, seqrunID should be replaced by the actual names). Options for the file extension type of the datatypes is provided in Column H.
 * Naming and/or description copied from the guidelines section of the FAIR project (<https://doi.org/10.1002/edn3.10100>)

A. Datasets/ Datatype	B. Description	C. Workflow step eDNAAqua-Plan landscape	D. Methodology	E. Metadata standard vocabulary (if applicable)	F. Repository/data management system	G. Standardised name (for digital files)	H. File extension
Project metadata *	Information that applies to an entire project and dataset. This includes a project name, reference associated to the datasets from which the datasets were derived (e.g., bibliographic references to studies, DOI of published, associated data), and metadata describing workflows including PCR, sequencing, and bioinformatic steps.	Start	Metabarcoding/ Metagenomics/ targeted assays	FAIRe, DwC	NCBI Bioproject/EINA BioProject/GBIF/OBIS	projectMetadata_project_id	csv
Sample metadata *	Information for each sampling event, including sampling date, location, methodologies, and environmental variables (i.e., temperature, water depth), this is the metadata associated with the physical samples collected in the field/lab.	Sampling	Metabarcoding/ Metagenomics/ targeted assays	FAIRe/MixS	NCBI/EINA Biosamples/ GBIF/OBIS	sampleMetadata_project_id	csv
Additional environmental data	Additional environmental data that do not fit the FAIRe / MixS environmental metadata described in the "Sample metadata" line can be listed here (e.g., sediment grain size measurements, chemical pollutant concentrations).	Sampling	Metabarcoding/ Metagenomics/ targeted assays	ENVO/NVS (NERC Vocabulary Server)/LLTER	NCBI/EINA Biosamples/ GBIF/OBIS	EnvironmentalData_project_id	csv
Samples for eDNA	The physical samples that have been collected for eDNA analyses such as water, sediment, air, feces, filters, gauze material from passive eDNA samplers, ...	Sampling	Metabarcoding/ Metagenomics/ targeted assays	GGBN	in house management systems (LMS, ...); the physical collection of samples can be unlocked digitally through the GGBN		
Samples for bulkDNA	The physical samples that have been collected for bulkDNA analyses (e.g., macrofauna, meiofauna, microfauna); these are typically preserved in ethanol; these samples can be analysed morphologically before bulkDNA extraction	Sampling	Metabarcoding/ Metagenomics/ targeted assays	GGBN	in house management systems (LMS, ...)		
Samples for morphological analyses	The physical samples that have been collected for morphological ID of the species (e.g., macrofauna, meiofauna, microfauna). These samples are often preserved on formaline and cannot be used for DNA-based analyses.	Not applicable	Morphology	DwC	in house management systems (LMS, ...)		
Samples for environmental measurements	The physical samples that have been collected for environmental measurements (e.g., sediment grain size, water chemistry, non-target-screening) in case these are different from the eDNA samples.	Sampling	Chemistry/lab measurements	No standard vocabulary, all samples should receive a unique ID	in house management systems (LMS, ...)		
Experimental conditions	A detailed description of the experimental set-up (e.g., treatments, replication, control conditions) in case samples were obtained from controlled experiments in the lab/field (as opposed to samples collected under natural, non-manipulated conditions)	Sampling	Metabarcoding/ Metagenomics/ targeted assays	Not applicable	open data repositories (e.g., Zenodo, Dryad, Figshare)	experimentLabMetadata_project_id	csv, docx
Sampling protocols	The protocols with a detailed step-by-step description of how the samples were collected	Laboratory procedures	Metabarcoding/ Metagenomics/ targeted assays	MIOP	BeBOP, Protocols.io, workflow.hub, OBP, Zenodo		docx, markdown
Methodological protocols	The protocols with a detailed step-by-step description of how the samples were processed in the lab (lab protocols, starting from the sample until library preparation/vPCR/dPCR).	Laboratory procedures	Metabarcoding/ Metagenomics/ targeted assays	MIOP	BeBOP, Protocols.io, workflow.hub, OBP, Zenodo		docx, markdown
Extracted DNA	The physical DNA extracts obtained from the collected field or experimental samples.	Laboratory procedures	Metabarcoding/ Metagenomics/ targeted assays	GGBN	in house management systems (LMS, ...); the physical collection of samples can be unlocked digitally through the GGBN portal, DISSCO or GBIF		
PCR standard data *	Detailed information of PCR standards, including starting input quantity, Ct/Cq values, and standard curve parameters (e.g., efficiency, R2).	Laboratory procedures	targeted assays	FAIRe, MIQE	open data repositories (e.g., Zenodo, Dryad, Figshare)	stdData_project_id	
eLow Quant Data *	Outputs from the eLow Quant binomial approach for PCR standards if applicable (see Lesperance et al., 2021).	Laboratory procedures	targeted assays	FAIRe, MIQE	open data repositories (e.g., Zenodo, Dryad, Figshare)	eLowQuantData_project_id	
Targeted assay amplification data *	Raw amplification data of each PCR technical replicate performed on eDNA samples, as well as estimated copy numbers based on standard curves (if applicable) and detection status of targeted taxon in each biological replicate (field sample).	Laboratory procedures	targeted assays	FAIRe, MIQE	open data repositories (e.g., Zenodo, Dryad, Figshare)	ampData_project_id_assay_name	
Libraries for sequencing	The physical sequencing library or libraries prepared from the DNA samples, ready to be sequenced and tagged to distinguish different samples.	Laboratory procedures	Metabarcoding/ Metagenomics	Not applicable	in house management systems (LMS, ...)		
Experiment/run metadata *	Sample-specific information for PCR, library preparation and sequencing workflows; contains for each sample the sample ID, Library_id, Multiplex identifiers (MID forward, MID reverse)	Laboratory procedures	Metabarcoding/ Metagenomics	FAIRe, MixS	NCBI/EINA Bioprojects/GBIF/OBIS	experimentRunMetadata_project_id	csv
Raw DNA sequence data *	DNA sequences in FASTQ format, demultiplexed for each sample. The sequences of primers, adapters and MIDs must be removed.	Laboratory procedures	Metabarcoding/ Metagenomics	MixS	NCBI/EINA/DDBJ		FASTQ
Metagenome assemblies	Raw metagenomic sequencing reads can be assembled into contigs (primary metagenome), binned into single taxon assemblies (binned metagenomes), or assembled into unique single taxon genomes (MAGs)	Bioinformatic Analysis	Metagenomics	MixS	NCBI/EINA/DDBJ		FASTA, SQN, JAGP
Bioinformatic code	A file or files containing the code used to process the raw sequencing data until the curated ASV/OTU/sequence table; for metabarcoding data, information on parameter settings for the various steps (cleaning, merging, denoising, clustering) should be added in the FAIRe metadata excel file to ensure reproducibility of the bioinformatic pipeline. DOIs of the file(s) should be documented in data accessibility statements within journal articles, as well as in the metadata term seq_bioinformatics of the FAIRe metadata excel file	Bioinformatic Analysis	Metabarcoding/ Metagenomics	FAIRe, DwC, MIXS, CodeMeta	GitHub, WorkflowHub		markdown, R, python
Data processing code	A file or files containing the code used in the data analyses (statistics, alpha and beta diversity measurements, figures and plots, ...). DOIs should be documented in data accessibility statements within journal articles, as well as in the metadata terms such as code_repo in the FAIRe metadata project excel.	Bioinformatic Analysis	Metabarcoding/ Metagenomics/ targeted assays	FAIRe, CodeMeta	GitHub, Zenodo, Dryad		markdown, R, python, bash
Raw ASV/OTU table *	The initial ASV/OTU table produced in a bioinformatic pipeline, containing absolute sequence read counts of all ASV/OTUs (including contaminant/non-targeted taxa and unassigned ASVs/OTUs) across all samples (including controls). Each ASV/OTU will be provided with a unique seq_id at this stage.	Bioinformatic Analysis	Metabarcoding	Not applicable	open data repositories (e.g., Zenodo, Dryad, Figshare)	otuRAW_project_id_assay_name_seqrunID	csv, xml, rdf
Processed ASV/OTU table *	An ASV/OTU table resulting from various data curation processes, including denoising (i.e., custom or LULU curation), removing control samples, and eliminating suspected contamination and non-target taxa. This table should ideally be identical to, or correspond closely to, the one used for the final (e.g. ecological) analyses published in associated scientific papers. ASVs/OTUs without taxonomic assignments should remain in the otuFinal table if they were relevant to the analyses.	Bioinformatic Analysis	Metabarcoding	Not applicable	GBIF/OBIS	otuFINAL_project_id_assay_name_seqrunID	csv, xml, rdf
Reference library	The custom reference file(s) containing the reference sequences and taxonomy or the public database that was used for taxonomic assignment of the sequencing reads; the version of the reference database should be clearly mentioned; for custom reference files, the DOI of the file should be documented in data accessibility statements within journal articles, as well as in the metadata terms OTU_db, custom of the FAIRe metadata excel file.	Taxonomic Assignment	Metabarcoding/ Metagenomics	WoRMS, eDNAAqua-Plan, FADA (freshwater database)	GitHub, WorkflowHub, Zenodo, Dryad, Figshare	refdb_project_id_assay_name	FASTA
Custom reference library code	A file containing the code to create the custom reference database; this should include information on the species list used to obtain the reference database, as well as any curation steps that have been performed to ensure reliable reference sequences (e.g., to identify low taxonomic resolution, or sequences that form paraphyletic clades); there is no specific metadata field in the FAIRe metadata template, but the DOI can be added to code_repo.	Taxonomic Assignment	Metabarcoding/ Metagenomics	Not applicable	GitHub, WorkflowHub, Zenodo, Dryad, Figshare		markdown, R
Non-curated sequence/taxa table *	In addition to the contents in the curated Sequence - Taxa table (below), this table includes ASVs/OTUs that were excluded from the curated ASV/OTU table (e.g., non-target taxa, contaminants, positive control sequences, ASVs with no taxa hits). It may also contain multiple rows for a single ASV/OTU assigned to multiple taxa, with information of each assigned taxon.	Taxonomic Assignment	Metabarcoding/ Metagenomics	Not applicable	open data repositories (e.g., Zenodo, Dryad, Figshare)	taxRAW_project_id_assay_name_seqrunID	tsc, csv
Curated sequence/taxa table *	DNA sequence of each seq_id listed in the curated ASV/OTU table. If a taxon was assigned, also include assigned taxonomy and assignment quality assurance parameters (e.g., % identity, % query coverage). If multiple taxa are assigned to a single ASV/OTU, the lowest common ancestor should be used as the assigned taxon.	Taxonomic Assignment	Metabarcoding/ Metagenomics	FAIRe, DwC	GBIF/OBIS	taxFINAL_project_id_assay_name_seqrunID	csv
Species occurrence data from morphological analyses	The taxa occurrence table obtained from the morphological analyses, with abundances/biomass of all taxa that were morphologically identified listed per sample.	Not applicable	Morphology	WoRMS, FADA, DwC	GBIF/OBIS	taxMORPH_Project_id	csv